

Trace-element signatures and U-Pb geochronology of magmatic and hydrothermal titanites from the Petrovitsa Pb-Zn deposit, Madan region, Central Rhodopes (Bulgaria)

Georgi Milenkov, Rossitsa Vassileva, Sylvina Georgieva, Valentin Grozdev, Irena Peytcheva

Geological Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Acad. G. Bonchev Str., Bl. 24, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria;
e-mails: georgimilenkov7@gmail.com; rosivas@geology.bas.bg; sylvina@geology.bas.bg; val.grozdev@gmail.com;
irena.peytcheva@erdw.ethz.ch

(Received: 15 June 2022; accepted in revised form: 25 August 2022)

Abstract. The current study presents new geochronological and geochemical data for the Petrovitsa Pb-Zn deposit, Central Rhodopes, South Bulgaria. Based on *in-situ* U-Pb dating of titanites from pegmatites and skarnified mineralized marbles, it aims to provide new insights into the pegmatite formation and their relation to the hydrothermal system in the region. Titanite is an abundant accessory mineral in pegmatites and skarns within the Madan ore district. Commonly, it associates with feldspars, epidote, clinopyroxene, chlorite, hematite, zircon, apatite, allanite and monazite in both lithologies. Crystal size varies from 5 μm to 600 μm . The combined analytical approach revealed compositional and age variations of the studied titanites divided into: (i) early formed magmatic; and (ii) later hydrothermal. The magmatic crystals are characterized by mean Th/U of 1.91, Lu/Hf averaging at 0.59, and Dy/Yb of 2.03. The chondrite-normalized REE patterns show LREE dominance over HREE. The average ΣREE is 6548 ppm. The hydrothermal titanites have a mean Th/U of 0.22, Lu/Hf of 1.20, and average Dy/Yb of 1.50. HREE content slightly prevails over LREE. ΣREE is two times lower compared to magmatic titanites – 3388 ppm. Negative Eu-anomaly is common for both types. The LA-ICP-MS U-Pb geochronology shows a well-defined age distinction of magmatic and hydrothermal titanites. The calculated U-Pb weighted average age for the magmatic titanites is 48.9 ± 2.3 Ma, while the pegmatite-hosted hydrothermal titanites are dated at 39.2 ± 1.5 Ma. The hydrothermal titanites from skarns yield a weighted average age of 37.7 ± 1.3 Ma. Data suggest pegmatite emplacement in the Rhodope metamorphic complex during the late Ypresian. Later hydrothermal fluids precipitated younger titanites with different signature.

Milenkov, G. Vassileva, R., Georgieva, S., Grozdev, V., Peytcheva, I. 2022. Trace-element signatures and U-Pb geochronology of magmatic and hydrothermal titanites from the Petrovitsa Pb-Zn deposit, Madan region, Central Rhodopes (Bulgaria). *Geologica Balcanica* 51 (2), 79–91.

Keywords: trace elements, U-Pb dating, titanites, pegmatites, Central Rhodopes, Bulgaria.

INTRODUCTION

The Cenozoic polymetallic deposits in the Central Rhodopes have been Bulgaria's major producer of Pb and Zn ($\pm\text{Ag}$) for decades. Most of the large deposits are located in the Madan and Laki ore districts in

southern Bulgaria (Fig. 1a, b). The ore bodies in the Madan area have produced more than 100 Mt of ore since 1940, with average grades of 2.54 wt% Pb and 2.1 wt% Zn (Milev *et al.*, 1996). The economic sulphide mineralization of vein and metasomatic type (Vassileva *et al.*, 2009; Milenkov, 2019; Hantsche

et al., 2021, and references therein) is hosted by the Rhodope metamorphic complex. The source of the mineralization and potential link to magmatism is still debatable. However, the underground mining operations in the last years have disclosed in-depth abundance of large pegmatite bodies within the metamorphic sequence.

Pilot studies described the mineralogical (Bogdanov, 1960; Dimitrov and Kotev, 1967; Cherneva *et al.*, 1997), geochemical and geochronological (Arnaudov *et al.*, 1969, 1990a, b; Cherneva *et al.*, 1995)

features of various magmatic and pegmatitic formations from the present surface in the Central Rhodopes. Based on the genetic classification suggested by Ivanov (1991), the pegmatites observed in this area belong to the rare earth group, corresponding to NYF or mixed type according to Černý and Ercit (2005). However, the characteristics of pegmatites from the underground ore deposits have been poorly studied through the years (Ivanov, 1991).

Recent studies on the pegmatite mineralogy and geochemistry (Bovay, 2016; Milenkov *et al.*, 2020,

Fig. 1. a) Tectonic map of Bulgaria (modified after Ivanov, 2017). b) Geological map of the Central Rhodopes and the main ore districts and deposits (Dimov *et al.*, 2000; Vassileva *et al.*, 2009). c) District-scale geological map with deposit locations (modified after Ivanov *et al.*, 1987; Hantsche *et al.*, 2021).

2022) revealed the abundance of titanite crystals occurring in both pegmatite and skarn environment in the deposits of the Madan and Laki districts. The current study attempts to clarify the age and potential origin of the pegmatites and their relation with the surrounding metamorphic lithologies in the Petrovitsa Pb-Zn deposit, Madan district (Fig. 1c). The abundant titanite accessory population is very suitable for the purpose because of its high closure temperature (up to 700 °C) and diffusion resistance (Ronald Frost *et al.*, 2000). Important geochemical characteristic of the mineral is the significant incorporation of Th and U contents in its structure (Ronald Frost *et al.*, 2000), which makes titanite an ideal geochronometer. Last but not least, titanite is a repository mineral for rare earth elements (REE) and high field strength elements (HFSE) in metamorphic, hydrothermal and magmatic environments. The study on titanite trace element composition can act as a tracer of former geological processes and can, therefore, be used as a provenance fingerprint, genesis indicator and time constraint.

GEOLOGICAL SETTING

The study area is a part of the Rhodope Mts. in South Bulgaria (belonging to the Rhodope Massif according to Ivanov, 2017, or the Rhodope Metamorphic Complex according to Ricou *et al.*, 1998; Fig. 1a), whose tectonic evolution and structure have been interpreted by a large number of authors, producing different tectonic models (*e.g.*, Ricou *et al.*, 1998; Burg, 2011; Janák *et al.*, 2011; Jahn-Awe *et al.*, 2010, 2012; Ivanov, 2017; Kounov *et al.*, 2020, and references therein). Generally, the existing tectonic models are based on broad, first-order subdivisions reconstructing paleogeographic arrangements, subduction polarity, stacking order, timing of the subduction of the involved terranes (Jan-Awe *et al.*, 2012), but nevertheless agree on the early compressional and later extensional stages in the Rhodopes' evolution. According to the major subdivision of the Rhodope Metamorphic Complex into Lower, Middle, Upper and Uppermost allochthons (Janák *et al.*, 2011) based on the ages of orthogneiss protholiths, regional deformation, high pressure metamorphism and overlying sediments, the ore-hosting Madan Unit (Ivanov *et al.*, 2000; Sarov *et al.*, 2007) belongs to the Middle Allochthon of the Rhodope Metamorphic Complex (Jahn-Awe *et al.*, 2010, 2012).

The Madan ore district is hosted in the uplifted and exposed Gondwana-derived metamorphic base-

ment sequence of the Rhodope Metamorphic Complex (Burg, 2011). Multiple low-angle detachment fault systems (Kounov *et al.*, 2020, and references therein) in the Central Rhodopes juxtapose the major tectonic units (Arda, Madan and Asenitsa; Sarov *et al.*, 2007; Fig. 1b) composed of lithologies with different metamorphic grades. The lower Arda Unit comprises orthogneiss composed of metamorphosed in granulite facies Late Paleozoic granitoids. The overlying Madan Unit is composed of biotite gneisses, amphibolites and marbles, whereas Asenitsa is built of parametamorphic rocks (generally thick marble units and gneisses), which suffered metamorphism in lower amphibolite facies (Sarov *et al.*, 2007).

Post-collisional extensional tectonics and related magmatism began locally at ~42 Ma with the intrusion of the Smilyan granite (and equivalents to the east; Kaiser-Rohrmeier *et al.*, 2013) and later phases of the Rila–West Rhodopes batholith to the west (Peytcheva *et al.*, 1998), shifting towards extension-related rhyolite dikes and ignimbrite deposit emplacement (Smolyan Basin) at ~31 Ma, as demonstrated by U-Pb dating of magmatic zircons (Ovtcharova *et al.*, 2003; Kaiser-Rohrmeier *et al.*, 2013). Skarn formation and sulfide mineralization in the Madan ore district have been constrained between 31.41 ± 0.39 Ma (U-Pb dating on zircon in rhyolite; Hantsche *et al.*, 2017) and 29.95 ± 0.23 Ma (Ar-Ar dating on hydrothermal sericite; Kaiser-Rohrmeier *et al.*, 2004).

The ore mineralization in the Madan district is controlled by a series of NW-trending, transtensional fault systems. The Petrovitsa deposit (located 5 km south of the town of Madan) is situated on a northwest-trending regional structure (Mogilata–Osikovo–Karaaliev Dol–Petrovitsa–Erma Reka fault) and represents one of the six remaining mining operations within the district (Fig. 1c).

Quartz-sulphide veins and rich skarn-ore metasomatic bodies hosted by the high-grade metamorphic rocks are the main base metal source of the deposits in the area. The quartz-sulphide veins are qualified as the main ore bodies. Their thickness varies from 0.1 m up to 15 m, whereas, depending on the geological setting, the veins can either increase or decrease their thickness in depth. These mineralized structures are hosted in gneisses which are pervasively altered to sericite-quartz and epidote-chlorite alteration assemblages (Milenkov, 2019; Milenkov *et al.*, 2019). The main ore minerals are galena, sphalerite and chalcopyrite, and galena prevails over sphalerite. The chalcopyrite content in the veins is higher compared to the meta-

somatic replacement ore bodies. The gangue minerals filling the veins are mainly pyrite, carbonates and quartz (Vassileva *et al.*, 2009, and references therein; Milenkov, 2019; Milenkov *et al.*, 2019).

Where the feeders crosscut marble lenses, the carbonate environment is skarnified. The process of skarn formation follows two stages: (i) prograde skarn stage, characteristic with occurrence of a

johannsenite-hedenbergite clinopyroxene and minor rhodonite assemblage; (ii) retrograde stage, in which the prograde assemblage is replaced by association of amphiboles, pyroxenoids, ilvaite, quartz and carbonates, and which favors the sulphide deposition of galena, sphalerite, chalcopyrite and pyrite. Sphalerite generally prevails over galena in the metasomatic replacement bodies of the Madan

Fig. 2. Studied outcrops in the Petrovitsa deposit: a) mine level 865; b) mine level 820; c) close view of (b) indicative of the position of sections MN-23-A and MN-23-4.

district (Vassileva *et al.*, 2009; Milenkov, 2019; Milenkov *et al.*, 2019; Hantsche *et al.*, 2021).

The skarn-ore bodies are lithologically controlled and have irregular shape, sometimes elongated in one direction. Usually, the processes of metasomatic replacement occur up to 15–20 m away from the main faults. Larger bodies are formed on crossings of ore-controlling structures. Rarely, replacement ore bodies were also formed in the amphibole-biotite gneisses or amphibolites. Typical textures for this type of ore bodies are impregnations, rhythmic banding, radial and massive (Vassileva *et al.*, 2009, and references therein; Milenkov, 2019).

Abundant massive pegmatite bodies (up to 2 m thick) are commonly observed as concordant or crosscutting injections relative to the main metamorphic foliation in the gneisses, amphibolites, and marbles (Fig. 2a, b). The primary mineral assemblage within the pegmatites is K-feldspar, plagioclase (anorthite, oligoclase, albite), micas and quartz, while titanite, allanite, zircon, apatite and monazite are accessories (Milenkov *et al.*, 2022). The secondary mineral association is represented by clinopyroxene, chlorite, epidote group minerals, sericite, kaolinite, rutile, leucosene, adularia and calcite. These alteration minerals, developed on pegmatites, are similar to those in the gneisses hosting the quartz-sulphide vein mineralization – epidote-chlorite and quartz-sericite assemblages. Some pegmatite bodies show mineral and geochemical internal zonation. Calcium-bearing minerals (*e.g.*, anorthite, epidote, clinozoisite, allanite, titanite and apatite) are formed mainly in the outer zone, closer to the metamorphic rocks (often marbles), which are sporadically skarnified (Fig. 2).

METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of the current study, we sampled two outcrops in the Petrovitsa deposit. Sample Pt-6 is from a pegmatite body on level 865 (Fig. 2a), whereas sample MN-23 (Fig. 2b) was taken from a mine gallery on level 820 and contains both skarnified marble (section MN-23-A) and pegmatite (section MN-23-4; Fig. 2c).

The mineralogical and textural peculiarities of the double-polished thin-sections were studied via optical microscope and scanning electron microscopy (SEM-BSE regime). Major element compositions of titanite were studied with Electron Probe Micro-Analyzer (EPMA) at the University of Geneva. The carbon-coated samples were analyzed using the EPMA model JEOL8200 Superprobe, equipped

with a 5 wavelength dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (WDS). The working conditions were an accelerating voltage of 15 kV, a beam current of 40 nA, and a beam diameter of 2 μm . Garnet (Y), La-phosphate (La), andalusite (Al), MnTi alloy (Ti), Ce-phosphate (Ce), forsterite (Mg), Th dioxide (Th), wollastonite (Si), MnTi alloy (Mn), Nd-phosphate (Nd), wollastonite (Ca), Ce-phosphate (P) and fayalite (Fe) were used as standards. Laser ablation inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS) at the Geological Institute of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences was used for determination of trace element composition and U-Pb geochronology. The system consists of a 193 nm ArF excimer laser (ATLEX-SI, Germany) linked with an ELAN DRC-e ICP-MS instrument (Perkin Elmer, Canada). Energy density on sample $\sim 9 \text{ J/cm}^2$, a repetition rate of 5, and ablation craters of 20 μm or 35 μm (depending on the available area) were applied as standard conditions. As primary external titanite standard for dating was used MKED1 and for zircon – GJ1. NIST 610 and 612 glasses were used to standardize tracing element compositions. The dating results were calculated using Iolite combined with Visual Age to obtain ages and ratios corrected for instrumental drift and down-hole fractionation. Correction for common lead was applied before recalculating the titanite age (Andersen, 2002). The plots were processed using ISOPLOT. SILLS program was used for data reduction and calculation of the chemical composition. Electron Probe Micro-Analyzer-measured SiO_2 content in titanite was used as internal standard.

RESULTS

Mineralogical features of the titanites in the Petrovitsa deposit

The studied titanite crystals highly vary in size and shape (Table 1). In both the pegmatite and the skarn samples, the mineral is associated with feldspar, minerals from the epidote group, clinopyroxene, chlorite and sometimes hematite (Fig. 3a). In samples MN-23-4 and MN-23-A, some of the titanite crystals show a good example of syn-kinematic formation by marking the metamorphic foliation (Fig. 3b).

Titanites in sample Pt-6 are crosscut and displaced by clinozoisite (Fig. 3c). Most of the studied euhedral titanite crystals do not display any obvious chemical inhomogeneity in BSE images, although there are some exceptions where patchy chemi-

Table 1
Characteristic features of titanites from the Petrovitsa deposit

Sample	Pt-6	MN-23-A	MN-23-4
Occurrence	Pegmatite body	Skarnified marble	Pegmatite body
Size and shape	20–600 μm ; Euhedral, subhedral; often cracked and with inclusions	5–500 μm ; subhedral to anhedral; mostly fresh, grouped (marking foliation)	10–600 μm ; Subhedral, anhedral, and irregular grains; partially cracked with inclusions and/ or patchy zonation; mostly grouped and arranged
Major elements, wt%			
Al ₂ O ₃	1.7–3.0	1.9–4.1	1.8–3.1
SiO ₂	30.8–31.1	30.8–31.9	30.2–31.5
CaO	27.9–28.7	27.9–29.5	28.0–29.3
TiO ₂	36.2–37.9	33.4–37.3	35.3–37.9
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.2–0.6	0.2–0.7	0.2–0.5
MnO	≈ 0.1	≈ 0.1	≈ 0.1
P ₂ O ₅	0.2–0.4	0.2–0.3	0.2–0.4
Minor and trace elements, ppm			
Sc	6–10	2–30	2–20
V	343–694	232–568	153–413
Cr	465–1049	316–2646	55–1139
Zn	28–93	10–123	8–102
Ga	29–110	9–45	12–37
Sr	28–41	17–155	14–40
Y	1097–1718	937–5599	490–9435
Zr	387–818	256–617	236–982
Nb	267–888	549–7331	499–8536
Mo	6–96	7–40	6–50
La	417–1292	57–682	61–259
Ce	1182–3233	274–2419	326–1324
Pr	159–452	49–343	74–271
Nd	672–1949	239–1484	408–1614
Sm	175–438	75–399	108–583
Eu	42–96	20–71	19–71
Gd	184–396	81–643	102–914
Tb	33–60	15–146	15–193
Dy	218–351	115–1054	90–1538
Ho	42–65	27–209	16–343
Er	118–188	99–611	49–1068
Tm	15–25	17–96	6–153
Yb	103–180	138–659	50–1001
Lu	14–23	18–78	6–112
Hf	17–47	11–45	16–179
Ta	10–127	18–809	20–1819
W	26–94	9–35	5–63
Th	178–669	24–565	25–78
U	156–308	120–771	98–919
Geochemical ratios (average values)			
Th/U	1.91	0.23	0.21
Dy/Yb	2.03	1.24	1.88
Lu/Hf	0.59	1.31	1.06
ΣREE	6548	3078	3830

Fig. 3. Occurrence of the titanites and their relationship with other minerals: a) microphotograph of hydrothermal alteration on pegmatite from sample MN-23-4/N; b) BSE image of titanites marking foliation (sample MN-23-A); in the upper right corner – clustered accessory minerals; green and red dashed lines show the foliation trends; c) BSE image of crosscut and displaced titanite (sample Pt-6); d) BSE image of inhomogeneous titanite crystals (sample MN-23-4); red points from 1 to 9 show where the EPMA analyses have been obtained, while on the diagram are presented the results of the major oxide contents. Abbreviations: Px – clinopyroxene; Chl – chlorite; Hem – hematite; Ttn – titanite; KFs – K-feldspar; Cz – clinzoisite; Ser – sericite; Ca – carbonates; Qtz – quartz; Aln – allanite; Zr – zircon; Ap – apatite; Plag – plagioclase; S – foliation.

cal zonation can be observed, as in section 23-4 (Fig. 3d). The higher amount of Al^{3+} and Y^{3+} and the lower contents of Ca^{2+} and Ti^{4+} are responsible for the brighter zones within the crystals (Fig. 3d, Table 2). Sometimes, different accessory minerals tend to form clusters in the pegmatites (Fig. 3b).

Geochemical features of the titanites in the Petrovitsa deposit

Table 1 shows the chemical compositions of titanite from the three studied sections. The major el-

ements' content does not vary much between the analyzed samples (see also Appendix A). The TiO_2 correlates negatively with the sum of $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ (Fig. 4a), indicating the following substitution: $(\text{Fe}, \text{Al})^{3+} + (\text{OH}, \text{F})^- \Leftrightarrow \text{Ti}^{4+} + \text{O}^{2-}$ (Li *et al.*, 2010, and references therein).

Vanadium, Ga, Zr, Mo, W and Th show higher contents in Pt-6 compared to section MN-23-A and MN-23-4 (Fig. 4b, Appendix B). Almost all measured elements in Pt-6 show lower amounts compared to the other samples (Fig. 4b). Both sections from sample MN-23 show a geochemical

Table 2
Major element composition of the analyzed points in Fig. 3d

Sample, wt.%	MN-23-4-tt-3-1	MN-23-4-tt-3-2	MN-23-4-tt-3-3	MN-23-4-tt-3-4	MN-23-4-tt-3-5	MN-23-4-tt-3-6	MN-23-4-tt-3-7	MN-23-4-tt-3-8	MN-23-4-tt-3-9
Y ₂ O ₃	0.22	0.85	0.50	0.61	0.63	0.12	1.04	0.30	0.44
La ₂ O ₃	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00
Al ₂ O ₃	2.72	3.06	2.76	2.90	2.79	2.61	3.02	2.58	2.57
TiO ₂	36.18	35.33	36.02	35.92	36.42	36.53	35.48	36.80	36.78
Ce ₂ O ₃	0.08	0.07	0.04	0.17	0.05	0.10	0.13	0.07	0.08
MgO	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
ThO ₂	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.00
Si ₂ O	31.26	30.93	31.25	31.15	31.37	31.49	30.97	30.83	31.38
MnO	0.07	0.08	0.03	0.10	0.04	0.07	0.08	0.06	0.05
Nd ₂ O ₃	0.09	0.05	0.03	0.14	0.02	0.09	0.20	0.18	0.07
CaO	28.82	27.95	28.65	28.29	28.95	28.94	28.06	28.87	28.37
P ₂ O ₅	0.22	0.23	0.21	0.30	0.22	0.21	0.29	0.23	0.22
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.34	0.41	0.34	0.30	0.26	0.34	0.38	0.29	0.29
Total:	100.07	98.94	99.85	99.89	100.74	100.51	99.69	100.21	100.24

Sample, apfu	MN-23-4-tt-3-1	MN-23-4-tt-3-2	MN-23-4-tt-3-3	MN-23-4-tt-3-4	MN-23-4-tt-3-5	MN-23-4-tt-3-6	MN-23-4-tt-3-7	MN-23-4-tt-3-8	MN-23-4-tt-3-9
Y	0.004	0.015	0.009	0.011	0.011	0.002	0.018	0.005	0.008
La	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Al	0.104	0.119	0.106	0.112	0.106	0.100	0.117	0.099	0.098
Ti	0.886	0.875	0.883	0.881	0.886	0.890	0.874	0.901	0.898
Ce	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.001
Mg	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Th	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Si	1.018	1.019	1.019	1.016	1.014	1.020	1.015	1.004	1.018
Mn	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.003	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.001
Nd	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001
Ca	1.005	0.986	1.001	0.989	1.003	1.004	0.985	1.007	0.986
P	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.008	0.006	0.006	0.008	0.006	0.006
Fe	0.004	0.005	0.004	0.004	0.003	0.004	0.005	0.003	0.004

similarity, although the titanites are from two different geological environments. Contents of REE, Nb, Ta, and Zr, commonly present in the Ca- and Ti-sites of titanite structure (Della Ventura *et al.*, 1999). Two different trends can be distinguished using the chondrite-normalized REE diagrams (Fig. 4c). Sample Pt-6 has narrow spread with LREE prevailing over HREE and an average sum of the total REE 6548 ppm. The other two sections (MN-23-A and MN-23-4) show the opposite trend, where their spread is wider, HREE prevail over LREE and the average sum of REE is 3078 ppm for MN-23-A and 3830 ppm for MN-23-4. Negative Eu-anomaly is the only common characteristic of all the studied samples. Important geochemical ratios, such as Th/U (Fig. 4d), Dy/Yb and Lu/Hf, are shown in Table 1. Similar to the rest of the analyses, identical values are observed for sections MN-23-A and MN-23-4, whereas Pt-6 shows few times higher ratios for Th/U, Dy/Yb, Σ REE and lower for Lu/Hf.

U-Pb age of the titanites in the Petrovitsa deposit

The titanites from sample Pt-6 yield a Concordia age of 49.45 ± 0.95 Ma. However, it has a very high mean square weighted deviation (MSWD) (Fig. 5a). Excluding anomalously high and low obtained ages and based on 20 analyses, the weighted average data display a mean value of 48.9 ± 2.3 Ma (Fig. 5b).

The analyzed titanites from the skarn body (sample MN-23-A) have a lower intercept age of 37.6 ± 2.4 Ma. The concordant yielded age is 39.1 ± 1.9 Ma with relatively high MSWD (Fig. 5c). Based on 23 analyses, the weighted average age is 37.7 ± 1.3 Ma (Fig. 5d).

Eighteen analyzed points in titanites from the pegmatite in sample MN-23-4 yield a lower intercept age of 38.2 ± 1.3 Ma. The obtained concordant age from 14 points is 40.2 ± 2.8 Ma (Fig. 5e), while

Fig. 4. Geochemical features of the titanites in the Petrovitsa deposit: *a*) TiO_2 is reversely-correlated with $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ for both magmatic and hydrothermal titanite, indicating the substitutions of $(\text{Fe}, \text{Al})^{3+} + (\text{OH}, \text{F})^- \leftrightarrow \text{Ti}^{4+} + \text{O}^{2-}$; *b*) Comparison of minor and trace-element concentrations within the titanites of the different studied samples; *c*) Chondrite-normalized REE patterns; *d*) plots of Th/U versus total REE.

the weighted average method indicates an age of 39.2 ± 1.5 Ma (Fig. 5f).

The obtained data on the concordia and weighted average ages of the samples can be found in [Appendix C](#).

DISCUSSION

The studied titanites in pegmatite and skarn bodies from the Petrovitsa deposit display two different stages and sources of formation. The geochemical peculiarities correspond to the yielded age distinction.

Titanites from sample Pt-6 have geochemical features as $\text{Th}/\text{U} > 1.50$ (indicating magmatic origin – Gao *et al.*, 2012), $\text{Dy}/\text{Yb} > 2.00$ (suggesting HREE depletion), $\text{Lu}/\text{Hf} > 0.30$ (characteristic of a magmatic origin – Li *et al.*, 2009), high ΣREE concentrations (average 6548 ppm), negative Eu anomaly (Pan *et al.*, 2018, and references therein). These features, along with the combination of field and microscopic observations, indicate magmatic origin of the studied minerals. The obtained U-Pb age sug-

gests that the pegmatite was intruded at ~ 50 Ma in the Madan Unit. This event could be linked to the magmatism in the Middle Allochthon of the Rhodope Metamorphic Complex (Janák *et al.*, 2011; Froitzheim *et al.*, 2014; Petrik *et al.*, 2016). The range of age data and high MSWD yielded from this sample could be explained by the loss of Pb related to further stages of fluid percolation which rejuvenated the titanites. However, these events do not affect the geochemical characteristics of the sample, through which we conclude its magmatic origin. Zircon- and allanite-rich bedded migmatitic pegmatites, hosted by the gneisses of the same unit along the Vacha River, show U-Pb ages between 58–49 Ma (Arnaudov *et al.*, 1990a; Cherneva *et al.*, 1995). Rare metal pegmatites crosscutting the metamorphic sequence near the village of Dolen, Zlatograd District, show uraninite U-Pb ages in the time span of 53–49 Ma (Arnaudov *et al.*, 1990a). Granitic magmatism in the metamorphic units of the Middle Allochthon, showing similar ages, is reported for the Pripek granites 52.8 ± 0.89 Ma and Drangovo pluton 49.9 ± 0.42 Ma (Marchev *et al.*, 2013, and references therein). These events coincide with

Fig. 5. Concordant and weighted average ages of titanites in: a, b) sample Pt-6; c, d) sample MN-23-A; e, f) sample MN-23-4.

the wider range of 56–40 Ma granitoids and pegmatites in the units of the same allochthon in Central (Dolno Dryanovo granite – 56 Ma; Jahn-Awe *et al.*, 2010), Eastern (Topolovo – 52.5 Ma; Marchev *et al.*, 2013) and Western Rhodopes (Vishteritsa pegmatite – 47.57 ± 0.32 Ma, Peytcheva *et al.*, 2021; 50 ± 5 Ma, Arnaudov *et al.*, 1969; and NW Rila area, Gorinova *et al.*, 2019).

The analyzed titanites from both lithologies (*i.e.*, skarn and pegmatite) in sample MN-23 (Fig. 2c) show very similar geochemical characteristics and age of formation. In both samples, the Th/U ratio is very low (< 1.50 , indicating hydrothermal or metamorphic origin – Scibiorski *et al.*, 2019, and references therein), Dy/Yb < 2.00 (suggesting LREE depletion), and the Σ REE concentrations average at 3078 ppm for MN-23-A and 3830 ppm for MN-23-4, which show a tendency towards hydrothermal origin. The occurrence and relationships of the studied accessory minerals with other products within the hydrothermal association (*e.g.*, clinopyroxene, epidote, chlorite, hematite, sericite, carbonate and kaolinite) in the pegmatite confirm earlier precipitation of titanite. Epidote is interpreted as post-genetic and accommodates preferentially LREE in its structure, which could explain the overall depletion in LREE in the studied titanites. A recent study based on hydrothermal titanites in altered gneisses on the contact with marbles from the Petrovitsa and Gyudyurska mines (Bovay, 2016) shows very similar geochemical features (low Th/U ratios and Σ REE concentrations) and almost identical age of formation (37.65–39.69 Ma) that reinforce our theory. The metamorphic foliation marked by titanites in sample MN-23 and the clustered distribution of the other accessory minerals could be explained with a syn- or post-metamorphic deformational event related to the studied rocks. However, evidence based on the mineral relationships and chemical composi-

tion suggests that the titanites are not product of the metamorphism.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the geochemical and geochronological data, two genetic titanite types, occurring in pegmatite environment, have been defined – magmatic and hydrothermal, with ages of formation of ~ 50 Ma and ~ 40 Ma, respectively.

Hydrothermal skarn-hosted titanite crystals show the same geochemical characteristics as the pegmatite-hosted hydrothermal titanite, and similar, slightly younger age of formation.

Considering field relationships, obtained ages, and geochemical peculiarities, the studied pegmatite bodies in the Petrovitsa Pb-Zn deposit are clearly pre-ore. Although the source of the metals in the Madan hydrothermal system is still controversial, the new data on the pegmatites in depth could bring insight into the crustal magmatism in the region.

Acknowledgements

This study is financially supported by the project KP-06-N34/4 of the Bulgarian National Scientific Fund and contributes to the project ERA-MIN3 PEGMAT (KP-06-DO02/2). We would like to thank the reviewers Assoc. Profs Zlatka Cherneva and Neven Georgiev (Sofia University), for their corrections that helped to improve the quality of the manuscript.

Appendices A–C. EPMA, LA-ICP-MS and U-Pb geochronological data (available online at https://www.geologica-balkanica.eu/sites/default/files/supplementary/Milenkov_Geol_Balc_51-2_2022_Appendices.zip).

REFERENCES

- Andersen, T. 2002. Correction of common lead in U–Pb analyses that do not report ^{204}Pb . *Chemical Geology* 192 (1–2), 59–79, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2541\(02\)00195-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2541(02)00195-X).
- Arnaudov, V., Amov, B., Baldjieva, T., Pavlova, M. 1990a. Tertiary migmatitic pegmatites in the Central Rhodope crystalline complex. Uranium-lead zircon dating. *Geologica Balcanica* 20 (6), 25–32.
- Arnaudov, V., Amov, B., Cherneva, Z., Arnaudova, R., Pavlova, M., Bartnitsky, E. 1990b. Petrological-geochemical and lead-isotope evidence of Alpine metamorphism in the Rhodope crystalline complex. *Geologica Balcanica* 20 (6), 29–44.
- Arnaudov, V., Amov, B., Pavlova, M. 1969. On the absolute geological age of certain pegmatites in South Bulgaria. *Bulletin of the Geological Institute, Series Geochemistry, Mineralogy and Petrology* 18, 19–27 (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Bogdanov, B. 1960. Geological structure of Madan ore region. *Annuaire de l'Institut de minéralogie et géologie* 1–2, 3–43 (in Bulgarian).

- Bovay, T. 2016. *Distal johannsenite-hedenbergite skarns as an ore-forming environment: Madan, Bulgaria*. MSc thesis, University of Geneva, 138 pp. (unpublished).
- Burg, J.P. 2011. Rhodope: From Mesozoic convergence to Cenozoic extension. Review of petro-structural data in the geochronological frame. *Journal of the Virtual Explorer* 39, 1–44, <https://doi.org/10.3809/jvirtex.2011.00270>.
- Černý, P., Ercit, T.S. 2005. The classification of granitic pegmatites revisited. *The Canadian Mineralogist* 43, 2005–2026, <https://doi.org/10.2113/gscanmin.43.6.2005>.
- Cherneva, Z., Arnaudova, R., Iliev, T., Rekalov, K. 1997. Feldspar thermometry of migmatitic formations from the Central Rhodopes. *Review of the Bulgarian Geological Society* 58 (3), 139–156 (in Bulgarian).
- Cherneva, Z., Dimov, D., Stancheva, E., Daieva, L. 1995. Sub-solidus and anatectic veins in migmatitic gneisses from the Vacha River valley, Central Rhodopes. *Review of the Bulgarian Geological Society* 56 (3), 91–109 (in Bulgarian).
- Della Ventura, G., Bellatreccia, F., Williams, C.T. 1999. Zr- and LREE-rich titanite from Tre Croci, Vico Volcanic complex (Latium, Italy). *Mineralogical Magazine* 63 (1), 123–130.
- Dimitrov, D., Kotev, D. 1967. Microclitic pegmatites. *Review of the Bulgarian Geological Society* 28 (2), 208–214 (in Bulgarian).
- Dimov, D., Dobrev, S., Ivanov, Z., Kolkovski, B., Sarov, S. 2000. *Structure, Alpine Evolution and Mineralizations of the Central Rhodopes Area (South Bulgaria)*. Guide to Excursion (B), ABCD-GEODE 2000 Workshop, Borovets, Bulgaria, 50 pp.
- Froitzheim, N., Jahn-Awe, S., Frei, D., Wainwright, A., Maas, R., Georgiev, N., Nagel, T., Pleuger, J. 2014. Age and composition of meta-ophiolite from the Rhodope Middle Allochthon (Satovcha, Bulgaria): A test for the maximum-allochthony hypothesis of the Hellenides. *Tectonics* 33 (8), 1477–1500, <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014TC003526>.
- Gao, X.-Y., Zheng, Y.-F., Chen, Y.-X., Guo, J. 2012. Geochemical and U–Pb age constraints on the occurrence of polygenetic titanites in UHP metagranite in the Dabie orogen. *Lithos* 136–139, 93–108, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lithos.2011.03.020>.
- Gorinova, Ts., Georgiev, N., Cherneva, Z., Naydenov, K., Grozdev, V., Lazarova, A. 2019. Kinematics and time of emplacement of the Upper Allochthon of the Rhodope Metamorphic Complex: evidence from the Rila Mountains, Bulgaria. *International Journal of Earth Sciences* 108, 2129–2152, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00531-019-01754-2>.
- Hantsche, A., Kouzmanov, K., Dini, A., Vassileva, R., Guillon, M., von Quadt, A., 2017. U–Pb age constraints on skarn formation in the Madan Pb–Zn district, Bulgaria: zircon evidence from Tertiary magmatism. *15th Swiss Geoscience Meeting, Abstract volume*, 124–125.
- Hantsche, A., Kouzmanov, K., Milenkov, G., Vezzoni, S., Vassileva, R., Dini, A., Sheldrake, T., Laurent, O., Guillon, M. 2021. Metasomatism and cyclic skarn growth along lithological contacts: Physical and geochemical evidence from a distal Pb–Zn skarn. *Lithos* 400–401, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lithos.2021.106408>.
- Ivanov, Ž., Sarov, S., Dimov, D., Klain, L., Mishev, E., Dragiev, C., Ilijev, K., Danchev, Z., Valchev, V. 1987. *Main characteristics and structure of the Madan ore field*. Geological Survey, Sofia, 25 pp. (unpublished report, in Bulgarian).
- Ivanov, I. 1991. *Granite Pegmatites in Bulgaria*. Bulgarian Academy of Sciences Publishing House, Sofia, 205 pp. (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Ivanov, Ž. 2017. *Tectonics of Bulgaria*. Sofia University Press, Sofia, 331 pp. (in Bulgarian, with English abstract).
- Jahn-Awe, S., Froitzheim, N., Nagel, T. J., Frei, D., Georgiev, N., Pleuger, J. 2010. Structural and geochronological evidence for Paleogene thrusting in the western Rhodopes, SW Bulgaria: Elements for a new tectonic model of the Rhodope Metamorphic Province. *Tectonics* 29 (3), <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009TC002558>.
- Jahn-Awe, S., Pleuger, J., Frei, D., Georgiev, N., Froitzheim, N., Nagel, T. 2012. Time constraints for low-angle shear zones in the Central Rhodopes (Bulgaria) and their significance for the exhumation of high-pressure rocks. *International Journal of Earth Sciences* 101, 1971–2004, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00531-012-0764-5>.
- Janák, M., Froitzheim, N., Georgiev, N., Nagel, T., Sarov, S. 2011. P–T evolution of kyanite eclogite from the Pirin Mountains (SW Bulgaria): implications for the Rhodope UHP Metamorphic Complex. *Journal of Metamorphic Geology* 29 (3), 317–332, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1525-1314.2010.00920.x>.
- Kaiser-Rohrmeier, M., Handler, R., von Quadt, A., Heinrich, C. 2004. Hydrothermal Pb–Zn ore formation in the central Rhodopian dome, south Bulgaria: review and new time constraints from Ar–Ar geochronology. *Swiss Bulletin of Mineralogy and Petrology* 84 (1), 37–58.
- Kaiser-Rohrmeier, M., von Quadt, A., Driesner, T., Heinrich, C.A., Handler, R., Ovtcharova, M., Ivanov, Z., Petrov, P., Sarov, S.T., Peytcheva, I. 2013. Post-orogenic extension and hydro-thermal ore formation: High-precision geochronology of the central Rhodopian metamorphic core complex (Bulgaria-Greece). *Economic Geology* 108 (4), 691–718, <https://doi.org/10.2113/econgeo.108.4.691>.
- Kounov, A., Seward, D., Burg, J.P., Stockli, D. Wüthrich, E. 2020. Cenozoic thermal evolution of the Central Rhodope Metamorphic Complex (Southern Bulgaria). *International Journal of Earth Sciences* 109, 1589–1611, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00531-020-01862-4>.
- Li, J.-W., Deng D.-X., Zhou, M.-F., Liu, Y.-S., Zhao, X.-F., Guo, J.-L. 2009. Laser ablation ICP-MS titanite U–Th–Pb dating of hydrothermal ore deposits: A case study of the Tonglushan Cu–Fe–Au skarn deposit, SE Hubei Province, China. *Chemical Geology* 270 (1–4), 56–67, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2009.11.005>.
- Marchev, P., Georgiev, S., Raicheva, R., Peytcheva, I., von Quadt, A., Ovtcharova, M., Bonev, N. 2013. Adakitic magmatism in post-collisional setting: An example from the early-middle Eocene magmatic belt in southern Bulgaria and northern Greece. *Lithos* 180–181, 159–180, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lithos.2013.08.024>.
- McDonough, W.F., Sun, S.-S. 1995. The composition of the Earth. *Chemical Geology* 120 (1–3), 223–253, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2541\(94\)00140-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/0009-2541(94)00140-4).
- Milenkov, G. 2019. *Retrograde skarn formation and polymetallic mineralization in the Petrovitsa deposit, Madan district, Bulgaria*. MSc thesis, University of Geneva and Lausanne, 111 pp. (unpublished).
- Milenkov, G., Kouzmanov, K., Hantsche, A., Vassileva, R. 2019. Retrograde skarn formation and polymetallic mineralization in the Petrovitsa deposit, Madan district, South Bulgaria. *Review of the Bulgarian Geological Society* 80 (3), 77–79.
- Milenkov, G., Vassileva, R., Georgieva, S. 2022. Critical elements in allanite and titanite from pegmatites in the Petrovitsa Pb–Zn deposit, Central Rhodopes, Bulgaria. *16th Biennial Meeting of the Society for Geology Applied to Mineral Deposits (SGA), Abstracts*, 255–258.

- Milenkov, G., Vassileva, R., Peytcheva, I., Grozdev, V. 2020. U/Pb dating and trace element compositions in pegmatite-hosted titanite from the Petrovitsa Pb-Zn deposit, Madan district, South Bulgaria. *Review of the Bulgarian Geological Society* 81 (3), 90–92.
- Milev, V., Stanev, V., Ivanov, V. 1996. *Mining Production in Bulgaria*. Zemya-93 Press, Sofia, 196 pp. (in Bulgarian).
- Ovtcharova, M., von Quadt, A., Frank, M., Kaiser-Rohrmeier, M. 2003. Triggering of hydrothermal ore mineralization in the Central Rhodopean core complex (Bulgaria)–insight from isotope and geochronological studies on Tertiary magmatism and migmatization. In: Eliopoulos, D.G. (Ed.), *Mineral Exploration and Sustainable Development, Volume 1*. Millpress, Rotterdam, 367–370, <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003077503>.
- Pan, L.-C., Hu, R.-Z., Bi, X.-W., Li, C., Wang, C.-L., Wang, X.-S., Zhu, J.-J. 2018. Titanite major and trace element compositions as petrogenetic and metallogenic indicators of Mo ore deposits: Examples from four granite plutons in the southern Yidun arc, SW China. *American Mineralogists* 103 (9), 1417–1434, <https://doi.org/10.2138/am-2018-6224>.
- Petrik, I., Janák, M., Froitzheim, N., Georgiev, N., Yoshida, K., Sasinkova, V., Konecny, P., Milovska, S. 2016. Triassic to Early Jurassic (c. 200 Ma) UHP metamorphism in the Central Rhodopes: evidence from U–Pb–Th dating of monazite in diamond-bearing gneiss from Chepelare (Bulgaria). *Journal of Metamorphic Geology* 34 (3), 265–291, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jmg.12181>.
- Peytcheva, I., von Quadt, A., Kostov-Kytin, V., Kadiyski, M., Stavrev, M. 2021. U-Pb dating composition of columbite from Vishteritsa: Implication for timing of granite magmatism and rare-element granitic pegmatites in the western Rhodopes, Bulgaria. *Geologica Carpathica* 72 (3), 195–212, <https://doi.org/10.31577/GeolCarp.72.3.2>.
- Peytcheva, I., Kostiyin, Y., Salnikova, Y., Kamenov, B., Klayn, L. 1998. Rb-Sr and U-Pb isotope data for the Rila-Rhodopes batholith. *Geochemistry, Mineralogy and Petrology* 35, 93–105 (in Bulgarian).
- Ricou, L.-E., Burg, J.-P., Godfriaux, I., Ivanov, Ž. 1998. Rhodope and Vardar: the metamorphic and the olistostromic paired belts related to the Cretaceous subduction under Europe. *Geodinamica Acta* 11 (6), 285–309, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0985-3111\(99\)80018-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0985-3111(99)80018-7).
- Ronald Frost, B., Chamberlain, K., Schumacher, J. 2000. Spinel (titanite): phase relations and role as a geochronometer. *Chemical Geology* 172 (1–2), 131–148, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2541\(00\)00240-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-2541(00)00240-0).
- Sarov, S., Voynova, E., Moskovski, S., Jelezarski, T., Naydenov, K., Nikolov, D., Georgieva, I., Petrov, N., Markov, N. 2007. *Explanatory note for the geological map of the Republic of Bulgaria in scale 1:50 000, K-35-86-G (Madan) map sheet*. Bulgarian National Geological Survey, Sofia, 46 pp.
- Scibiorski, E., Kirkland, C.L., Kemp, A.I.S., Tohver, E., Evans, N.J. 2019. Trace elements in titanite: A potential tool to constrain polygenetic growth processes and timing. *Chemical Geology* 509, 1–19, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemgeo.2019.01.006>.
- Vassileva, R.D., Atanassova, R., Bonev, I.K. 2009. A review of the morphological varieties of ore bodies in the Madan Pb-Zn deposits, Central Rhodopes, Bulgaria. *Geochemistry, Mineralogy and Petrology* 47, 31–49.